

The Psychological Aspect of Rasain Sanskrit Literature

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Abstract:

Rasa -theory is the climax of Indian literature criticism where 'art' for 'art-sake' and 'art means preaching' both the principles are accomplished and the concepts of sub-wiltedness and purposefulness relating to poetic expression are also meet with. Rasa is the only concept which is supposed to be present in almost all the poetic elements, like, Guna, Alankara, Dhvani, Vakrokti, Anumiti, and even poetic blemishes (Kavyadosa). It is in this sence that Rasa is the fundamental (Svarupadhyaka) eliment of the Kavya. The expression, like, Angin, Sanjñin, Jivita and Atman used for Rasa only Indicate it's all pervading nature (Sarvatattvavyapita). In this way, the history of Rasa became so wide that it could permeate the whole of poetics.

There has developed a tradition to deal Rasa as an element as well as a theory, and as such it has evolved as an independent school of poetics. Rasa is only element which possesses a universal appeal and so is widely considered the essence of all the forms of literary expression. although a lot of works has been done on the Rasa and gradual study has been going on tis different aspects by Indian and foreign scholars in different language also, but some of its aspects to which proper justice has not yet been done while some of its problems require further elucidation. The present work is an effort to explore such aspects and throw necessary light on them.

Key Words: Rasa, Kavya, Dosa, Guna, Riti, Vrtti, Vakrokti, Pravrtti, Rasa, Kavya, Dosa, Guna,

Riti, Vrtti, Vakrokti, Pravrtti, padarthah, Vasanas, Kavyananda, Sahridaya, asvadya, Sthayibhava, Udreka, Rasika, mano-bhava, Dharma, atman, Adhikari, Vakyartha, Rasanubhuti, Cittavrtti, Citisakti, Parinama, Citta, Buddhi, Sukha, Duhkha, Moha.

Introduction:

"What is rasa?" This question has been the subject of discussion of sahrdayas and the scholar even to-day. Many independent books were written and even now are being written. Many theories connected with rasa were developed and are being developed even now. The more it is discussed the more it is becoming a secret and a subject of curiosity. In this age of scientific advancement, scholars other than the literatures are not making any attempt to understand rasa; it has remained the subject of curiosity of them. In spite of all this there is no change in the habit of reading the kavyas, in seeing the dramas and in enjoying the rasa. people continue to experience rasa. Therefore, such question like "what this experience is?" "how it is produced?" arise naturally.

Here an attempt is made to analyse the nature of rasa and the scientific process involved in its experience. The question "what is rasa?" is as old as the history of the kavyasastra itself. Bharata in the sixth chapter of natyasastra raises the question "atrasa rasa itika?" – It is asked what is rasa?" He gave the replay also पदार्थ इत्युच्यते १. It is called a padarthah.? Here 'padarthah' does not mean 'a thing' it means "vakyartha." (the purport of the sentence). This point has been made clear by Abhinavagupta – rasa is the kavyartha, because it (rasa) makes the kavyartha enjoyed and contemplated upon. Thus, rasa only is the padartha:

तथा द्याह कार्व्यार्थान् भावयन्ति इति तत्काव्यार्थो रसः
१२

Thus, the padarthah.e.kavyartha is the rasa. What is the proof for it? The replay of the natyasastra is "asvadyatvat". Only the kavyartha is enjoyed through the kavya, and rasa is being enjoyed through the kavya, and so it is the kavyartha:

आस्वादनात्मानुभवो रसः काव्यार्थ उच्यते १३

The Bhavas are known, with that name because they make us contemplate upon the

Kavyartha through the mental articulate and physical gesticulations.

वाग्दसत्त्वोपेतान् काव्यार्थान् भावयन्तीति भावाः ॥४

Much has been written on the point whether Rasa is to be relished (asvadya) or it is the relish (asvada) itself. If it is said asvadya the experience would become objective whereas it is subjective only. If the Rasa is the experience of something external then it should become the object of the cognition for everybody including a rustic and the animals. But it is the experience of the Sahridayas only and so it can be definitely said that it is not the object, the cognition of which is produced through its contact with the senses. Moreover, the objective cognition generally differs on account of the difference of the place, time and person etc., and cause pleasure, pain or inertia. But the Rasa experience is only blissful and only a fortunate person gets it. That person is said to be fortunate because the Rasa-experience is produced only by the Vasanas (mental impressions) which are inherited from the previous birth and also acquired now. One can enjoy the Kavyananda only when these two types of the Vasanas exist in him. In the absence of one type of the Vasana, he cannot get it. It shall be shown later on that Rasa is the experience of the emotions latent in one's mind.

It may be asked why then, the Rasa is said to be asvadya in the Natyasastra in statements like रस इति कः पदार्थः उच्यते, आस्वाद्यत्वात्, etc.? By the use of the passive voice in "Katham asvadyaterasa?" it is clearly indicated that the Rasa is the object of enjoyment. It is true; but when it is established, in the Natyasastra itself, that enjoyment by the Sah?daya of his own latent permanent emotions (Sthayibhavas) is the Rasa, the expressions like and "asvadyatvat" "asvadyate" etc., should be taken as the secondary usages (Lakkanika Prayogas), as is explained by Visvanatha on the analogy of "OdanahPacyate" etc. Therefore, Rasa is only the experience but not a thing to be experienced; it is subjective but not objective.

As the Natyasastra explains the medium of the Rasa experience is only the mind but not the senses. There are eight permanent moods

like the Rati in our minds which are generally latent. When they are roused it is called their 'Udrekā' and they are experienced at that state only. Their Udrekā is brought about in two ways - when we come across certain exciting objects which instigate them or when such objects are presented through a poem or a drama. When excited by the Kavya or Na?aka etc., they become the objects of the experience directly through the mind. As it is said in the following Karika, Rasa is the experience of the Sthayibhavas like Rati, latent in the mind of the Sah?daya and are excited by the Abhinaya (gesticulation etc.):

भावाभिनयसंबद्धान् स्थायिभावांस्तथा बुधाः ।
आस्वादयन्ति मनसा तस्मान्नाट्यसाः स्मृताः ॥६

Thus, the experience of one's own Bhavas (emotions) is called Rasa. The descriptions in a Kavya and the scenes in a drama, only excite them and make them enjoyable. This is what is meant by the phrase 'asvadyantimanasa' (experienced mentally) in the above karika. Therefore, Rasa should be called subjective but not objective. It is not the Dharma (quality) of any object that is experienced; it is the Dharma of the spectator himself who experiences and so his mano-bhava (mental state). The Rasa is the experience of the latent emotions roused by the scenes in a drama or by the descriptions in a Kavya; and so, it is not their Dharma. Contrary to this the peculiar vasana in the mind of a person, which is one of his Dharma (quality) is enjoyed in the form of the Rasa. If a person experiences one of his own Dharmas (quality) that experience should definitely be taken as subjective but not objective. That is why the Rasa is said to be confined only to the Rasika (man of fine taste) and as born of the blissful atman:

रसः स एव स्वाद्यत्वाद्रसिकस्यैव वर्तनात् ।
स्वादः काव्यार्थसंभेदात्मानन्दसमुद्भवः ॥७

This point is further clarified by Dhanañjaya. While the children play with the toys; like the horses and the elephants etc., made of clay, though they know that they are not the real horses and elephants, forget the fact and get the enjoyment as though they are dealing with the real ones. The secret of this enjoyment is they are at that time enjoying their

own utsaha. The same thing happens with the spectator also. He experiences and enjoys his own emotions like the utsaha, which are roused by the characters like Arjuna described in the kavya or presented in the natya:

क्रीडतां मृण्मयैर्यद्द् बालानां द्विरदादिभिः ।
स्वोत्साहः स्वदते तद्वच्छ्रोतृणामर्जुनादिभिः ॥८

The experience of the Bhavas like Utsaha is referred here by the 'Svadate' which means that the experience is the relish. Abhinavagupta, while analysing, perhaps Bhattanayaka's statement "kavyenarasabhavyante" writes "yat kavyenarasabhavyanteityucyatetatra vibhavadi-janita-carvanatmakasvadarupa-pratyaya-gocaratapadanamevayadibhavanamtadabhyupagamyataeva".

If by saying the Bhavana (the aesthetic contemplation) is produced by a kavya, it is meant that Rasa becomes the object of the blissful cognition which is in the form of relishing (Carvanatmaka) produced by the Vibhavas etc., it is agreeable to us also. In the same context while commenting on the sentence "asvadanatmanubhavorasahkavyarthaucyate". (The cognition in the form of enjoyment is called Rasa and that is said to be the Kavyartha) he writes:

अनुभवेन च तद्विषय इति मन्तव्यम् ॥९

Kavyartha is the Vyangya because it is the Visaya (object) of the Vyapara (function), Vyañjana (suggestion). It is called Rasa because it is the experience in the form of relish. Thus, the Rasasvada is the combination of the cognition produced by the intellectual process and the experience produced by the mental comprehension. Therefore, only a person who, apart from being a man of great intuition (in sight) (Pratibha) possesses a pure heart is qualified (Adhikari) for the Kavya. Only such man can have the direct experience of the Kavyartha after recognising the Vakyartha (the sense of the sentence) on hearing verse like 'grivabha?gabhirama?' and "harastukiñcitpraviluptadhairya?" etc. This experience is called Svah?dayasa?vada i.e. the enjoyment of the object (Vi?aya) which is grasped by one's intellect and the relish of the bliss of the Atman affected by the association Kavyartha. Only such person who gets such experience is

called Sahrdaya:

येषां काव्यानुशीलनवशाद्विशदीभूते मनोमुकरे
वर्णनीयतन्मयीभावयोग्यता ते स्वहृदयसंवादभाजः
सहृदयाः ॥१०

As is clear from the above discussion, the Rasanubhuti is a mental experience. In other words, it is one's experience of one's own mental modifications (moods). When an external object comes into contact with the senses it invariably influences the mind. As a result of this the mind undergoes different modifications which are experienced by every person. Why this happens? The reply to this can be found in the Yogasastra. In the Yogadarsana, the modifications of the mind are given the name Cittavrtti. The control of the Cittavrttis is called 'Yoga', and so the Yogasastra makes a detailed analysis of the various Cittavrttis. In the context of the Rasanispatti and the Yoga, in both the cases, "Citta" means Buddhi (intellect) only but not the Citisakti (consciousness) or the H?daya, because the experience one gets, both in the Kavya and Yoga is assertive (Niscayatmaka) and it is called adhyavasaya. The cognition is the Dharma (quality) of the Citta; it is the basis for the procedure, and the Parinama (modification) takes place there only, but not in the Cittasakti (consciousness). Vacaspatimisra writes in his commentary on Yogabhasya -

चित्तशब्देन अन्तःकरणां बुद्धिमुपलक्षयति । नहि
कूटस्थानित्या चितिशक्तिरपरिणामिनी ज्ञानधर्मा
भवितुमर्हति, बुद्धिस्तु भवेदिति भावः ॥११

The Rasacarvana also is called a type of Pratyaya (cognition) by Abhinavagupta:

रसना च बोधरूपैव । किन्तु बोधान्तरेभ्यो विलक्षणैव ।
उपायानां विभावादीनां लौकिक — वैलक्षण्यात् । तेन
विभावादिसंयोगाद्रसना यतो निष्पद्यते ततस्तथा
विधरसनागोचरो लोकोत्तरोर्थो रस इति तात्पर्यं
सूत्रस्य ॥१२

The Citta where the Rasanubhuti takes place is not inert itself and other things. (Ja?a). It has the capacity to know Therefore the Rasanubhuti comes under the knowledge. That is why it is called anandamayasa?vit which means that we get that knowledge in form of bliss only with no distinction of "mine" or "other's". Thus, by making a comparative study of Yoga and the modifications (Vrttis) of the Citta which the locus of the Rasanubhuti much light

is can be thrown on the subtle and the imperceptible procedure of the Rasanubhuti.

There is one more point to be noted here. From the view-point of the desired result also the Yoga and Kavya have similarity. In both, the main purpose for which a man acts is the removal of the distress. The only difference is whereas the Yoga is useful for the removal of future distress (Du?ka), the scope of the Kavya is limited to the present only. The main purpose of the Yogasastra is हेयं दुःखमनागतम् ३

The distress of the past has already been suffered; the present one is being suffered. Therefore, they cannot be the object of the Yoga. Only the future distress can be avoided, and that is the main aim of the Yoga.' Contrary to this the main aim of the Kavya is to produce Sadya?-Paranirv?ti (immediate happiness) by making the Sah?daya forget himself and submerge in Ananda (happiness).¹ It can remove only the present distress. Thus, the removal of the distress by the Yoga is permanent whereas the one by the Kavya is momentary. People afflicted with various distresses of the world take rest for some time, enjoy happiness and after becoming themselves in their work. It is said in the Natyasastra: दुःखातानां श्रमार्तानां शोकातानां तपस्विनाम् । विश्रान्तिजननं काले नाट्यमेतद्धविष्यति १४

It is clear from the use of the word "Kale" here that the removal of the distress caused by the Kavya is there so long as the reading of a Kavya or its presentation continues; or till its influence persists. The next moment the man goes back to his original state of Sukha, Du?kha and Moha.

The Cittavrttis (Modifications of the mind)

In the Yogadarsana five Bhumis (stages) of the Citta are mentioned; they are Kripta (agitated), Vikripta (distracted), Mudha (inactive), Ekagra (concentrated) and Niruddha (controlled). The first three stages are commonly found in our day-to-day activities of life. The Citta of a man in the wakeful state (Jagratastavatha) is generally in the K?ipta-stage. In the dreams and at the time of inadvertence it is in the Vik?ipta-stage. In the deep sleep it is in Mudha-stage. One gets the fifth stage (Niruddha) in the Asamprajñatasamadhi (Samadhi where one is not conscious of any

object). The fourth stage, Ekagra, is the stage of the mind in the Samprajñatasamadhi (Samadhi where one is conscious of an object). This stage is connected with the wakeful state only. When a man is completely absorbed in an action or concentrates on an object, this state is called Samprajñatavastha. "Samyakprakar? enajñayateyasminnasau Sarprajñata? tadbhinna? Asamprajñata? These two stages, Ekagra and Niruddha are connected with the Samprajñatasamadhi and the Asamprajñatasamadhi respectively. In the Samprajñatasamadhi, as explained by Vacaspatimisra, the Vrttis coloured by Rajas and Tamas in the Citta are suppressed and only the Vrtti of the Sattva remains predominant. But in the Asamprajñatasamadhi the Vrttis of all the Gunas including the Sattva are suppressed. Thus, when all the Vrttis of the Citta are controlled, Asamprajñatasamadhi results and when the Sattva remains predominant there would be Samprajñatasamadhi:

रजस्तमोमयी किल प्रमाणवृत्तिः सात्त्विकीं वृत्तिमुपादाय सम्प्रज्ञाते निरुद्धा, असंप्रज्ञाते तु सर्वासामेव निरोध इति १५

While explaining the nature of the Samprajñatasamadhi it is said that this Samadi is associated with Vitarka (argumentation), Vicara (deliberation), Ananda (joy and Asmita (the sense of being). वितर्कविचारानन्दारिमितानुगमात् संप्रज्ञातः १६

When the mind is concentrated on a gross object (the Samprajñatasamadhi) is called "Vitarkanugata"; when it concentrated on some thought it is called Vicaranugata; with the Atman it is called 'Asmitanugata'. These are four varieties of the Samprajñatasamadhi. The Rasanubhuti of a Kavya also is a state of Samprajñatasamadhi which appears on the concentrated mind. As Ananda (joy) is object of this concentrated mind this comes under category of Anandanugatasamprajñatasamadhi. The concentration to hit a target is Vitarkanugata. The concentration on subjects like mathematics is Vicaranugata. The concentration of the mind while experiencing the blissful Rasa of a Kavya is the Anandanugatasamprajñatasamadhi. The concentration on the Atman resulting in the experience of "ahambrahmasmi" is the

Asmitanugata. All these four varieties of Samadhi come under Samprajñatasamadhi because there is the cognition of Vitarka, Vicara, Ananda and Asmita in them.

There should be no controversy in accepting the Rasa state of the Citta as Anandanugata-samprajñatasamadhi. There is so much of similarity between the procedural description, found in the Yogabhasya, of the Samprajñatasamadhi-state and the description of the state of Kavya-rasa-carvana. As is described in the Yogabhasya the Samprajñata Samadhi is that which makes a Sadbhuta-artha (a beautiful object) illuminated in the concentrated mind, destroys the Klesas, (hindrances) weakens the bonds of Karma and takes the mind towards the Niruddha-state:

यस्तु एकाग्रे चेतसि सद्भूतमर्थं प्रद्योतयति, क्षिणोति च क्लेशान्, कर्मबन्धनानि श्लथयति, निरोधमभिमुखं करोति, स संप्रज्ञातो योग इत्याख्यायते १७

While explaining the phrase सद्भूतमर्थं द्योतयति Vacaspatimisra writes:

भूतमिति समारोपितमर्थं निवर्तयति। निद्रावृत्तिरपि स्वावलम्बे तमसि भूते एकाग्रा इत्यत उक्तम्, सदिति शोभनं नितान्ताविर्भूतसत्त्वं तमस्समुद्रेकस्तु अशोभनस्तरस्य क्लेशहेतुत्वादिति १८

By saying "Bhuta' (existing) the super imposed object " excluded. Even the Nidrav?tti is the result of concentration on the Tamas of the Citta which its support is. The word "Sat used to exclude it (Nidrav?tti). Sat' means 'good and beauty where there is the predominance of the Sattva. The used to exclude it (Nidrav?tti). 'Sat' means 'good and beautiful where there is the predominance of the Sattva. The predominance of Tamas is not good, because it is the source of the Klesas. The Sat may be cognised either by the Tattva-jñana (the spiritual knowledge) or by the inference. In either case it can remove the Avidya (ignorance) not directly, but indirectly only.

As is clear from the above discussion the predominance of the Sattva in the mind is the Samprajñata-state. While explaining the procedure of the Bhojakatva-Vyapara, Bhattanayaka points out at this state only - "satvodrekaprakasanandamaya-sa?vid-visranti-satattvenabhogenabhujyate." This means-after the Sadhara?ikarana of the Vibhavadi the

Sattvagu?a in the mind of the spectator becomes predominant suppressing the Rajas and the Tamas. At that moment there will be some kind of brightness in the mind the experience of which is blissful. The same is called Anandamayasa?vit and the mind takes repose in this only. It will not have the cognition of anything else excepting that of one of the Bhavas like Rati. This state of Rasa-Carvana (the relish of the Rasa) may be analysed by dividing it, into three parts

1. Sattvodreka (predominance of Sattva)
2. Prakasanandamayasa?vit (the bright and blissful experience) and
3. Visranti (repose). The concentration of the mind in the Samprajñatasamadhi is brought about in three forms:

1. To make the good and beautiful object shine which, in other words, is the predominance of the Sattva after the Rajas and Tamas are suppressed;

2. The removal of the Klesas which is nothing but the Prakasanandamayasa?vit, and

3. The Citta becoming favourable to Nirodha which, in the words of Bhattanayaka, is the Visranti.

It is said that the bonds of Karma get slackened in the Samprajñatasamadhi. This is the same as the Sadhara?ikara?a as mentioned by Abhinavagupta - "Mamaivanamama; satroevanatasayatathata?asthasyaivaivata?asthasya". This acceptance and the negation of the special relation is on account of the absence of a deciding factor (Anadhyavasaya of Niyama) ममैवैते शत्रोरेवैते तटस्थस्यैवैते न ममैवैते न शत्रोरेवैते न तटस्थस्यैवैते इति सम्बन्धविशेषस्वीकार परिहारनियमानध्यवसायात् साधारण्ये न प्रतितैरभिव्यक्तः १९

What is meant by the "slackening of the bond of Karman is no doubt, that the Sa?skaras produced by the previous Karmas would become weak and ineffective in producing their results. But as a result of the Karmas done with the intention of getting something good or bad for himself or for others. some relationship like enmity or friendship is formed which is also a bond. At the time of Rasanubhuti these Bandhanas become lose. There would be no mental tension, caused by those bonds at that time.

Though these feelings do not disappear permanently they are kept in suspension at least for some time. They come back and find place in the mind of the man after sometime. Therefore, the basis for the Rasanubhuti from a Kavya is only the Anandanugatasa?prajñata-samadhi which is achieved by the mind of high concentration. There is difference in the varieties of the Sarprajñatasamadhi based on the gradational difference in the concentration. In the Vitarkanugata the Citta is concentrated on a gross subject, Sthula-visaya. In the Vicaranugata it is concentrated on some thought and so it is subtle than the Vitarkanugata. In the Anandanugata the concentration of the Citta is on the subtler objects like the latent impressions (Sa?skaras) and the emotions. This is the reason why Abhinavagupta calls the state of Rasasvada as the experience of the Rati etc., connected with the consciousness (Cidvisistaratyadi). PanditarajaJagannatha does not hesitate to call it "the consciousness associated with the Rati etc." (Ratyadyavacchinnacit). The Ratiyati is neither an object (Vastu) nor a thought connected with an external object, but they are the emotions in the form of the Sa?skaras (impressions) produced by those objects and the thoughts. Therefore, the concentration of the mind on them is blissful. In this stage there is contact with one's own consciousness, according to Abhinavagupta and the veil of ignorance is removed from the Atman according PanditarajaJagannatha. Therefore, this state can be called as the state of "Anandanugata-sa?prajñata-samadhi" and so those who call it an objective experience, taking the, Rasa as an object of cognition on the strength of the wordAsvadyatvat in the Natyasastra do not appear to be correct. If it is accepted as an object; it would come under the Vicaranugata but not Anandanugata. As it is the experience of the unalloyed bliss which is the Dharma of the consciousness, but not of an object (Vastu) or the thought, it is the experience in the form of Relish, and is not the object of relish. Therefore, it should come under the scope of the Anandanugata- sa?prajñata but not of the Vicaranugata-sa?prajñata.

The Process:

Yogasastra prescribes certain methods to take the Citta to the state of Nirodha. Only a pure Citta can be Sattvic and concentrated and enter into the state of Nirodha ultimately. It is said in the Yogabhasya:

प्रख्यारूपं हि चित्तासत्त्वं रजस्तमोभ्यां संसृष्टमैश्वर्यविषयप्रियं भवति । तदेव तमसा अनुविद्धम् अधर्माज्ञानावैराग्यानैश्वर्योपगं भवति । तदेव प्रक्षीणमोहावरणं सर्वतः प्रद्योतमानमनुविद्धं रजोमात्रया धर्मज्ञानवैराग्यैश्वर्योपगं भवति । तदेव रजो ले शमलापे तं स्वरूपप्रतिष्ठं सत्त्वपुरुषान्यताख्यातिमात्रं धर्ममेघध्यानोपगं भवति । तत् परं प्रसंख्यानमिति आचक्षते व्यायिनः ॥२०॥

The Citta is purified by suppressing the Rajas and Tamas and by making the Sattvapredominant. For this purpose, the Yogasastra has classified all the objects of the world into four categories and prescribed a method of pondering over them (Bhavana) in four different ways. The world is a jumble of Sukha, Du?kha, Pu?yaand Papa (happiness, affliction, merit and sin). Certain things in the world give pleasure, some cause misery, some are the source of Pu?ya and some of Papa. By maintaining four types of attitudes about these four varieties of things the mind gets purified by becoming Sattvic:

मैत्रीकरुणामुदितोपेक्षाणां सुखदुःखपुण्यापुण्यविषयाणां भावनातः चित्तप्रसादनम् २१

One should develop friendly attitude towards the happy persons, show pity to those afflicted with sorrows, and should be pleased with the people of merit (Pu?ya) and should have an attitude of indifference towards the sinful. By developing this type of attitude, one can acquire the sukladharma (Purerighteousness) by which the mind gets rid of all the impurities and becomes capable of concentration:

तत्र सर्वप्राणिषु सुखसम्भोगापन्नेषु मैत्रीं भावयेत्, दुःखितेषु करुणाम्, पुण्यात्मकेषु मुदिताम्, अपुण्यात्मकेषु उपेक्षाम्, एवमस्य भावयतः शुक्लो धर्म उपजायते, ततश्च चित्तं प्रसीदति, प्रसन्नम् एकाग्रस्थितिपदं लभते ॥२२॥

This state of the Citta is called Sthitisilata.

This section of the Yogadarsana is very useful to understand the procedure of Rasanubhuti laid down by Bharata. As has been mentioned earlier, there will be different types of reactions in the mind when there is contact

between the senses and the external objects. This reaction of the mind is always not the same. This can be in many ways depending on the nature of the instigating external objects. Therefore, the classification of these reactions depends on the nature of the external objects. The classification of the external objects into four groups, Sukhaspada (pleasant), Du?khaspada (distressing), Pu?yaprada (meritorious) and Papaprada (sinful) according to Yogasastra is shown above. The mental reactions in the form of Maitri (friendliness), Karuna (pity) Mudita (joy) and Upek?a (indifference) are given this fourfold classification on the basis of the nature of the external objects as explained above. Here the Maitri is connected with Sukha, Karuna with Du?kha, Mudita with Pu?ya and Upek?a with Papa.

As is clear, from the above discussion there is a possibility of only four types of mental reactions when it (the mind) is influenced by the external objects and they are Vikasa, Vistara, K?obha and Vik?epa. The mental reactions are nothing but the modification or changes in the mind. Let us now take up each one of them and examine.

A. Vikasa (Expansion):

This is a mental state, produced when there is contact of the senses with a person of Pu?ya or such object. At that time there arises the feeling of Mudita (joy) in the mind, and this is the indicative factor of this state. Like the bud of a flower which blooms and spreads fragrance in all directions the mind expands when it begins to enjoy the pleasure of Sattvaguna which keeps the person in a blissful state. Its experience onsets in the s??gararasa and the hasyarasa. It is said in the Natyasastra that whatever is, in this world, pure, pious, bright and beautiful is compared with the s??gararasa: यत्किञ्चित् लोके शुचिमेध्यमुज्ज्वलं दर्शनीयं वा तच्छङ्कारेणोपमीयते । २३

It is, therefore, but proper and is in accordance with the sastra that the external object which causes the Mudita-bhavana which is identical with the experience of S??gara should be good and pious (Pu?yaprada). The show of lust can never rouse the S??gara. Only a person of nobility and his actions can rouse it. Now a

question arises - is it acceptable to the Yogasastra, that the Prasadana (pleasing) of the mind which is its Vikasa is brought about by experience of the S??gara? In reply to this, it may be said that Yoga strives to remove the future distress whereas the Natya or the Kavya is meant for securing the Ananda through the removal of the present distress. Therefore, what is avoidable in the Yoga may be acceptable in the Na?ya or Kavya. The similarity is only in this aspect that the citta, in both of them, becomes concentrated being in the Sa?prajnata state.

B. Vistara (spreading)

Vistara is another reaction of the mind. When the senses come into contact with a pleasant external object then the mind gets Vistara (spreading). The word "Vistara" indicates the nature of the effect produced on the mind. It also implies the existence of a place on which something spreads. It means that the Citta spreads beyond the place of its existence. In other words, the Sattvagu?a of the Citta spreads throughout the body as a result of which every part of the body becomes alive. The Vistara of the mind is experienced through the feeling of Maitri which is mainly connected with the Vira and indirectly with the Adbhuta. The Vistara of the mind is felt When the Utsaha (high spiritedness), the Sathayibhava of the virarasa, energises every part of the body. Whenever we come under the influence of a pleasant object or a person we get so much of Utsaha which effects the Citta in the form of Vistara; as a result of which we cannot keep quiet and become very active. This is what is called Maitribhavana. The appearance of the Maitribhavana is the sign of Vistarawhich is possible through the direct or indirect contact with a pleasant person an object. Every good person makes friends with a per enjoying happiness. To be jealous of him is meanness. That is why Vira is said, in the Natyasastra as the nature of a noble person and as being produced by clear understanding determination, foresight, modesty and prowess etc: अथ वीरो नाम उत्तमप्रकृतिरुत्साहात्मकः स च असम्मोहाध्यवसायनयविनयः बलपराक्रमशक्तिप्रताप प्रभावादिभिः विभावैः उत्पद्यते । २४

C. K?obha (agitation)

Mind gets disturbed by distress. When the senses come into contact with an object which causes distress its reaction on the mind will be in the form of agitation which results in the Bhavana of Karuna. When the mind is disturbed there will be terrible conflict among the Sattva, Rajas and Tamas of which there will be a powerful impact on the nervous system. As a result of it other effects like weeping, crying and losing the consciousness take place. Weeping and crying bring back the mind to its normal condition as is said by Bhavabhuti:

शोके क्षोभे च हृदयं प्रलापैरेवधार्यते २५

In the agitated mind the feeling Karuna appears mainly in the Raudrarasa and less in the Karunarasa.

D. Vikrepa (distraction)

The distracted state of the mind produces the feeling of Upek?a (indifference). Its reaction would be in the form of disgust and fear which develop into Bibhatsa and Bhayanaka. The Vik?epa of the mind which causes Upek?a-bhavana is the result of the reaction of the contact with sinful external objects.

Conclusion-

As is clear from the above discussion it is proved that the Vikasa, Vistara, K?obha and Viksepa are the fundamental modifications or reactions of the Citta which are experienced in the form of the feelings, Mudita, Maitri, Karuna and Upek?a That is the reason why S?agara, Vira, Bibhatsa and Raudra a accepted as the fundamental Rasas in the Natyasastra. The other four Rasas-Hasya, Karu?a, Adbhuta and Bhayanaka are the side products of the above four Rasas. तेषामुत्पत्तिहेतवश्चत्वारो रसाः ।

तद्यथा — शृङ्गारो रौद्रो वीरो वीभत्स इति ।

अत्रशृङ्गाराद्धि भवेद्भारयो रौद्राच्च करुणो रसः ।

वीराच्चौवाद्भुतपत्तिर्बीभत्साच्च भयानकः ॥२६

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